

Rice land races from several provinces in China.

Province	No.
Anhui	725
Beijing	9
Fujian	1894
Gansu	7
Guangdong	4863
Guangxi	8967
Guizhou	4279
Hainan	668
Hebei	325
Heilongjiang	113
Henan	365
Hubei	1417
Hunan	5001
Jiangsu	2320
Jiangxi	2869
Jilin	68
Liaoning	78
Neimenggu	10
Ningxia	18
Shaanxi	642
Shandong	128
Shanghai	304
Shanxi	169
Sichuan	3255
Taiwan	1190
TianJin	27
Xinjiang	16
Xizang	38
Yunnan	5532
Zhejiang	1585
Total	46,882

negatively affects rice growth. The rice-growing area and the number of land races there are much less than those in areas to the south of the Chanjiang River. In the Huanghuai Plain, the land races are concentrated in the lower valley of the Huaihe River and the coastal regions where water resources are abundant.

The area near the Bohai Sea in Hebei Province, the lower valley of the Liaohe River in northeastern China, and the Songhuajiang River Valley are the main areas for rice land races in regions at high latitudes.

The climate in northwestern China is continental and dry with a short wet season. Rice land races are mainly—but sparsely—distributed over river valleys. They constitute only about 1% of all the land races in China. ■

Some suggestions for in situ conservation of wild rices

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India has seven species of wild rices. Four of these, *Oryza nivara*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. sativa* f. *spontanea*, and *Porteresia coarctata*, occur in the coastal and hilly districts of Uttara Kannada (13° 55' N to 15° 32' N latitude and 74° 5' E to 75° 5' E longitude) and Shimoga in Karnataka.

We examined 125 populations of wild rices to determine their habitat require-

ments and how ongoing ecological changes are affecting them. From 22 Oct 1992 to 6 Oct 1993, we collected seed and plant specimens from 43 locations and deposited them in a herbarium at the CES (see table).

Karnataka had not previously been explored for wild rices, so the intraspecific variation that remains can still be captured. Moreover, large patches of wild rices still exist that can be easily conserved in situ. These wild rices are locally known as *Nyarai*, *Nyarai batta*, *Kadu batta*, *Kadu hullu*, *Uddinakardi battu*, *Uddirige Urbu*, *Chungu Nyari*, and *Navane*.

A few plants of *P. coarctata* that were seen on 22 Oct 1992 at Kumta-Vannalli

Collection date, locality, and other information for some wild rice samples. Karnataka, India.

Collection date	Locality	Taluk ^a	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)	Habitat type ^b	Relative abundance ^c	Species ^d
22-10-92	Kumta-Vannalli	K	14°25.25'	74°24'	3.5	E	E	P
28-10-92	Dhadeshwar	K	14°25.5'	74°24'	3	S	F	s/n
06-10-93	Dhadeshwar	K	14°25.5'	74°24'	3	S	R	s/n
23-10-92	Handigon	K	14°23.5'	74°24.5'	4	F	A	s/n
23-10-92	Handigon	K	4°23.5'	74°24.5'	4	F	A	s/n
06-10-93	Handigon	K	14°23.5'	74°24.5'	4	F	E	s/n
28-10-92	Handigon	K	14°23.5'	74°24.5'	4	F	F	s/n
23-10-92	Handigon	K	14°23.5'	74°24.5'	4	F	A	s/n
30-10-92	Manki	K	14°26.75'	74°26'	5	C	R	s/n
23-10-92	Manki	K	14°26.75'	74°26'	5	F	A	s/n
06-10-93	Manki	K	14°26.75'	74°26'	5	F	O	s/n
05-11-92	Gudwi	So	14°27'	75°01'	550	P	A	n/r
06-11-92	Gudnapur	So	14°33'	74°59'	570	T	A	n/r
05-11-92	Yelasi	So	14°22'	75°03'	580	T	A	n/r
04-11-92	Kondli	Si	14°21'	74°54.5'	590	T	A	n/r
22-10-92	Sashitlu-Kumta	K	14°25.5'	74°24'	3.25	F	F	S
03-11-92	Mattigar	Si	14°18'	74°52.5'	580	F	A	S
03-11-92	Menasi	Si	14°17'	74°49'	580	F	A	S
03-11-92	Menasi	Si	14°17'	74°49'	580	F	A	S
03-11-92	Mattigar	Si	14°18'	74°52.5'	580	F	A	S
05-11-92	Tyavgod	So	14°25'	75°03'	585	T	A	r
04-11-92	Balekoppa	Si	14°21'	74°54'	590	T	F	r
04-11-92	Avragoppa	Si	14°22'	74°52'	585	T	A	r
04-11-92	Aigod	Si	14°24'	74°56'	570	T	A	r
06-11-92	Kantraji	So	14°22'	74°59'	555	T	A	r
05-11-92	Konan mane	So	14°22'	75°01'	560	T	A	r
04-11-92	Andawalli	So	14°22'	74°57'	570	T	A	r
04-11-92	Andawalli	So	14°22'	74°57'	570	T	A	r
03-11-92	Akkunji	Si	14°18'	74°53.5'	570	T	A	r
05-11-92	Kallambi	So	14°26'	75°02'	570	T	A	r
04-11-92	Andawalli	So	14°22'	74°57'	570	T	A	r
05-11-92	Sirlige	Si	14°21'	74°56.25'	575	T	A	r
05-11-92	Sirlige	Si	14°21'	74°56.25'	575	T	A	r
05-11-92	Hale Sorab	So	14°23'	75°05'	580	T	A	r
03-11-92	Kawachur	Si	14°16'	74°54'	580	T	A	r
05-11-92	Hale Sorab	So	14°23'	75°05'	580	T	A	r
03-11-92	Nagarbawi	Si	14°19'	74°51.8'	590	T	A	r
03-11-92	Hosur	Si	14°20'	74°53'	595	T	R	r
03-11-92	Hosur	Si	14°20'	74°53'	595	T	A	r
03-11-92	Hasvante	Si	14°14'	74°54'	595	T	A	r
05-11-92	Gundasettikoppa	So	14°22'	75°04'	595	T	A	r
03-11-92	Talguppa	Sa	14°13'	74°54.25'	615	T	A	r

^aTaluk is an administrative unit below the district level; K = Kumta, Si = Siddapur, So = Sorab, Sa = Sagar. ^bE = estuarine rice cultivation, F = farmer's field, P = pond, S = seasonal stream, T = tank. ^cA = abundant, F = frequent, O = occasional, R = rare, E = locally extinct. ^dn = *Oryza nivara*, r = *O. rufipogon*, s = *O. sativa* f. *spontanea*. p = *Porteresia coarctata*.

have already become locally extinct when a tidal wetland area was converted into prawn culture. Other wild rice populations are threatened by the encroachment of small irrigation tanks, freshwater aquaculture, and a change in the cultivation system from broadcasting to transplanting.

In situ conservation of these important genetic resources must be initiated and complement ex situ conservation efforts. These measures could include

- *Integration into conservation programs of tidal and freshwater swamps.* For example, the Karnataka State Forest Department has a program to conserve mangrove

swamps at Kundapur in Dakshina Kannada and a freshwater wetland at Gudwi Pakshidham in Shimoga. Other wetlands, such as those in Bharatpur in the state of Rajasthan, are being protected under the Ramsar Convention. Special attention should be paid to in situ conservation, including deliberately introducing into the wetlands appropriate indigenous wild rice species.

- *Integration into ecotourism-based conservation programs.* One of the study sites, Gudwi, is a bird sanctuary close to the tourist attraction of the Gerusoppa Waterfalls. Conservation

of wild rices, along with environmental awareness programs, could be effectively integrated with the tourist attraction of aquatic birds.

- *Use of indigenous knowledge.* Some local indigenous communities, such as the Mushahars of eastern Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, depend on wild rice grain and other wild foods for survival. These people have an intimate knowledge of the distribution and habitat requirements of wild rices. It would be highly useful to involve these communities in in situ conservation programs.

Panicle culture and karyotype analysis from callus cells of a diploid wild rice, *Oryza meyeriana*

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The genus *Oryza*, to which the cultivated rice (*O. sativa* $2n=24$) belongs, has 20 wild species with $2n=24$ or 48 chromosomes. *Oryza meyeriana* ($2n=24$) is highly resistant to bacterial blight. The karyotype of this species has not been well documented and only a few tissue culture studies have been made. We report the results of in vitro culture of young panicles and karyotype analysis of this species.

Embryogenic calli with high plant regeneration ability. We obtained embryogenic calli with high plant regeneration ability using N6 and MS

culture media alternately. The N6 medium contained 2 mg 2,4-D L^{-1} and 4.5% sucrose while the MS medium was supplemented with 2 mg kinetin L^{-1} , 0.5 mg NAA L^{-1} , and 3.0% sucrose. Green plant regeneration frequency of the selected calli was up to 76%, but that of the unselected calli was only 33% after the 10th culture. The free amino acids in the calli were determined. The methionine glutamic acid and the total amino acid contents in the selected calli were lower than those in the control, while the alanine and phenylalanine contents in the selected calli were higher than those in the control. The main components of the free amino acid pool in the selected calli were alanine, glutamic acid, and phenylalanine, which together constituted 65.8% of the total amino acids.

It appears that alanine, glutamic acid, methionine, and phenylalanine occupy a key position in amino acid metabolism and influence the regeneration capacity of calli.

High IAA oxydase activity was helpful in regenerating the calli.

The regenerated plants were tested for reaction to three bacterial blight strains: PXO61, T7174, and Jiang Ling 691. Fifty regenerated plants were inoculated with the three strains on different tillers of the same plant. The regenerated plants were resistant to the strains, but the degree of resistance differed among the plants.

Karyotype analysis. *O. meyeriana* has strong seed shattering and low seed fertility, making karyotype analysis using seed difficult. So instead, we used the method of Kurata et al to conduct karyotype analysis using calli.

The *O. meyeriana* had $2n=24$ (see figure). Based on the arm ratio, the karyotype of *O. meyeriana* consisted of 4 pairs of metacentrics, 7 pairs of submetacentrics, and a pair of satellite-submetacentric chromosomes (see table). ■

a) The somatic metaphase showing 24 chromosomes in *O. meyeriana*; b) the karyotype of *O. meyeriana* (x7000).